

Review Article

The Resources of CREATIVITY to reinforced Self Identification and to obtain Well-Being Whatever the previous psychic State and the Age

Hugues SCHARBACH. M.D

University; Neuro-psychiatrist, pedo-psychiatrist and National Expert hon Past Head of Psychiatric SERVICE in C.H.U.; Past TEACHER in University; Doctor of Psychology LYON's II's University; Expert hon

Corresponding author

Dr Hugues SCHARBACH: M.D. PARIS's University; Neuro-psychiatrist, pedo-psychiatrist and National Expert hon Past Head of Psychiatric SERVICE in C.H.U.; Past TEACHER in University; Doctor of Psychology LYON's II's University; Expert hon

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Abstract

Wellness describes a healthy lifestyle in which people have the energy and freedom to do that they want. Wellbeing includes the broader holistic of well-lived life. (GOOGLE)

Different was the Search of optimization of one's mental and psychic abilities, for the Fulness of One's Sense of Self, for well-being is very current but, Creative Expression has only been highlighted in terms of its benefits for the Improvement of mentally ill people, who, on their own, had discovered their particular potential and their preserved Skills and Creative Talent.

-The writing leading to literary elaboration, the paintings were more creative and especially freer, including strong affective and emotional feelings, than one would have supposed it during the time of very agreed and conformist states. It even appears that the description of aggression and violent affective situations is quite equal to the unconstrained freedom of mind that we can see in many shapes of Arts, even in sculpture, as "Solitude" in Institute of Arts in CHICAGO.

It's only in some Psychiatric Services that It became possible for patients to DRAWN and realize PAINTINGS, as well as they could be able also to develop their possibilities in to create in collage, modeling, cutting, embroidery and more often in Musical fields.

Different WORKS, with material both FABRICS, WOOD, PERLS (Louise BOURGEOIS and her intimate works, relative to: Moi, Eugénie GRANDET-(H. BALZAC) i.e. are becoming unforgettable as also Seraphine de SENLIS.

For instance, in literature: Antonin ARTAUD, which represents a body's writing", permitting to create links with his psychiatrists? By the work of the character, the desire may appear, the style being the realization of the fantasmatic according to J. LACAN 's conception...The fascinating text intitled: the "Schizo et les langues" of Louis WOLFSOM, who no longer supports to hear or to read in english.

-Famous became WORKSHOPS of SAINT-ANNE in PARIS. It's one of practitioners, Cl. WIART, around the mid-60s, who give me the idea to open a Workshop in my hospital, when I began my medical career. Similar care places will appear in other Hospitals such as the VINATIER, where Sylvain FUSCO should see interesting paintings.

With the Help of the works of my Patients, of their descriptions and comments of their Paintings, we should be able to write our Medical THESE (PARIS; 1968) under the Pts J.DELAY; P. DENIKER.), and a few later to write a book: Arts et Folie or: "Arts and MADNESS": 158 p.1988; always Relevant, to organize a Congress in NANTES's University. (1975). A Japanese Student was taking part and we receive always the Japanese Bulletin.

-Famous are also the descriptions of works realized by mentally -ill patients followed for care in the psychiatric Hospital of HEIDELBERG (GERMANY), such Normann SEIBOLD. H.PRINZHORN have gathered, exposed, realized a collection (eine Sammlung) of many works and written "Bildenerie der Geisteskranken als Kunstler" and "Grenzgänger zwischen Kunst und Psychiatrie". Famous also the works of Adolf WÖLFELI collected by MORGENTHALER in the WALDAU's Hospital in BERN (SWITZERLAND), As well as concerning patients receiving people with some particular psychic interest or living enough isolated have become famous apart with cares as painting "Friedrich der Einzige/Allein" "Alone" in BERLIN, Unica ZÜRN with the Enchanted princess". In Hauterives (DROME's department -FRANCE) Postman/factor CHEVAL was building alone his Palace), architectural plans by J.J LEQUEU. It could be possible to cite many others: "House of Picassiette (plate)" in CHARTRES...A lot of other ones as Norman Seibold...

A Social Reflection or attempt to remove an unbearable reality towards ill-persons should have appear.

KEY WORDS: Progectual capacity, (PC)- quantum physics – newtonian physics – neuronal network -thought

PREAMBLE

All that is preceded by some paradigmatic painting references, notably with the advent of Raw ART, which links figurative to pulsional expression.

The PERSEE's Mirror was necessary to dare watch Meduse and to behold her.

As was written RICKMAN in his article "The nature of Ugliness and the Creative Impulse", its necessary to consider the esthetic Aspects in other terms.

But, this space is auspicious for the ternary: real, imaginary, symbolism as paradigm in the studies of J. LACAN. Anchoring of epistemological works of Gaston BACHELARD... A kind of Borromean ring and it permits to shape, to weave exceptional exemplary creation, as well by the artist than the suffering people.

It's so important, that Art's teachers open since fifty years, school of Expression, as Erika STEINBERGER in New York, for instance.

INTRODUCTION

Paradigmatic Aspects from the old times: even long Before:

-Strong, pregnant Works, Positive EXPRESSIONS in the different Shapes of ARTS, driven by a psychologically dizzying creativity have been neglected, underestimated for a long period during which such subjects in mental suffering, hospitalized or leading a slow life, were relatively ostracized....

-It's only in some Impatient Psychiatric Care Ward or Services that It became possible for patients to DRAWN and realize PAINTINGS, as well as they could be able also to develop their possibilities in MUSICAL [15] and in different WORKS, with different material both FABRICS, PERLS (Louise BOURGEOIS, who tried an identification, painting: "Moi, Eugénie GRANDET", sculptures in WOOD, i.e.

In fact, that's a the end of the XIX's, in 1872 century that TARDIEU recognize that evident talent. In "Medico-legal study of the Madness, he described some creative Works, which, in his terms, take part of nightmare and make you dizzy, as an extraordinary art." Then, In 1876, Max SIMON published in Annales medico-psychologiques an important publication intitled "Imaginery of Madness" about Drawings, plans, suits of alienated. Then, ROGUES de FURSAC recognized a diagnostic value to these production and in 1907, REJA, published a paper intitled: "Mads's Arts" in "Mercure de France".

-With the Help of the works of my Patients, of their descriptions and comments about their Paintings, we should be able to write our Medical THESE (1968) R and a few later to write a book, intitled "Arts et Folie" "Arts and MADNESS": Cesura LYON ed; eBay; 158 p.1988; always Relevant, with a strange painting of an Octopus split according to the discordant disturbances of the thought of one in fronton. -Also, to organize a Congress in NANTES's University. (1975) and later, a big congress in TOULOUSE, with the contributive participation of 20 psychiatrists, whose articles have been brought in a book. A Japanese Student was taking part and we receive always the Japanese Bulletin.

-But, Famous also where before in other countries the descriptions of H. PRINZHORN "Bildeneri der Geisteskranken als Kunstler".in HEIDELBERG (GERMANY), as well as of Hans PRINZHORN: "Imagery of mentally ill patients" in Asylum of WALDAU (SUISSE) and also in other Asylum of specialized care, notably in MASSACHUSSETS (U.S.A.)

A great and original Psychopathological Expression was going to become Famous From people, who have been painting without education in that field as masters.

It's still a very important characteristics to evoke: the choice of the colors, their play and even a kind of sound, sad as grey mix or happy as different red. The painter of certain works can be recognized only by seeing his work far away.

For example, the works of schizophrenic patients are often overloaded.

-These princeps's elaborations were on different themes: strange, odd, weird or moving, unsound will help their promotion.

All these representations mixing sketch and symbolism evolved with artistic skills and talents should arouse, provoke a great fascination in reason of the apparent powerful transgression. They should be carried away and promoting dissemination new productions.

IMPACT of that free Creativity on the CULTURE and in the fields of ARTS

According to many publications, which were done in psychiatric congress bringing the commitment and almost passionate follow-up of drawing and painting.

-It the reason of which appears a new shape of Art, named ART BRUT or RAW ART followers of Adolf WÖLFLI, ALOÏSE CORBAZ even Gaston CHAISSAC; Jean DUBUFFET; Jean; Paul KLEE; Max ERNST; André BRETON; Henri DARGER; Augustin LESAGE; Magali HERRERA; Friedrich SCHRÖDER... fascinated by the apparent powerful transgression of people, who have been painting without education in that field.

It's still a very important characteristics to evoke: the choice of the colors, their play and even a kind of sound, sad as grey mix or happy as different red. The painter of certain works can be recognized only seeing his work far away.

-But apart places giving cares, people with some particular psychic interest have become famous as painters, as "Friedrich der Alleinig" in BERLIN; Postman/factor CHEVAL and his Palace in Hauterives (FRANCE) without to forget a lot of others.

Also, PICASSIETTE building his house near CHARTRES and the architectural planes of J.J. LEQUEU...

Resorting spontaneously, even instinctually, - imitating in some way the activity of the unconscious through dreams - allowed mentally ill people, the isolated, the lonely, to put movement of thoughts, of the body, to go ahead in controlling their affects and managing their emotions as well as possible...In short, to become a dynamic actor of oneself.

This pregnant materialization, as much of the forms, of the colors as the type of presentation, close to the archaic or rather first levels of the unconscious, like the dream, of such an authentic humanity, after their discovery, then their development, they were to become models of new forms of Art preceded by some significant painting references. : Vintage Art, Expressionist one, in a personal way, hyperrealism, surrealism, and, moved by various influences, crossing cubism and futurism of Salvador DALI ... And Jackson POLLOCK representative of the abstract expressionism, who may eliminate the time of the mental representation of the shape in favor of the direct projection of his emotions on the canvas in reason of a intime spiritual life of the painter, of the New York school as well as Mark ROTHKO attentive to formal elements such as color, shape, depth, i.e., then the Pop Art with artists as R. LICHTENSTEIN, A. WARHOL, C. OLDENBURG...

Later, in 1996, a museum, l'ARACINE will be created in Villeneuve d'Ascq, near LILLE (FRANCE) and one devolved to Art BRUT in LAUSANNE.

EMOTIONS DRIVE by WORKS BY Famous PAINTERS

Great painters proceed usually within a team; as MICHEL ANGELO,

REMBRAND, VELASQUEZ, i.e. It was not the context of occasional painters working with an exciting or thrilling idea. Emotion was in this extreme case mobilizing neuro-mediators as tryptophane/serotonin, nor-adrenaline and even endorphin.

I-Certainly, among painters, we can mention aspects of the work representing hard death's pulsions as it was described by M. KLEIN [5]. Francisco GOYA involving is savage, bloody representation with la Quinta del Sorbo (which could be showed in the PRADO Museum) "Los Desastres de la Guerra" may be a protestation against the Violence during the Dos de Mayo...

The Massacre/slaughter of CHIO by E.DELACROIX. That one is among the painters interested in the representation of anger: "Furius MEDEE; also: the "Cool Anger of Sévère " de GREUZE; The Big day of His Angry par John MARTIN". The angry act: by Per Lasson Krohg or also by REMBRAND: "Jésus chasing the merchants from the Temple "the Wrath of the Monster" by J.H. FÜSSL, who had also realized "Der Trauma des Schäfers- Shepherd's Dream" and Nightmare.

The Terror of hell by BOSCH

The Fear, the Cry: Edward MUNCH, who, in fact, was inspired after the big vulcan's eruption whatever distant... We add the painting of an anxious man, who, after having evoked a bad remembering in the frame of a psychotherapy, realized a disturbing work.

-The Sorrow felt by EVE and ADAM driven from the Paradise;

-The Hope and the bodies tortured in the Raft of the MEDUSA of GERICAULT

-Complex and raw impulses, enigmatically staged by BRONZINO in his painting: « VENUS and CUPIDON" containing number of encrypted details, involving different symbolic connotations affect with his perverse touches: ranging from jealousy to despair on the bottom of time, which weight down or the concern to preserve virtue. (Arts Gallery: LONDON)

Otherwise, many paintings of MICHEL-ANGE or of the CARAVAGGIO may appear unexpected by their freedom inherent in the scenes presented, or even by the underlying eroticism. Even NARCISSISMUS by D. Michel GLAIZE.

But we cannot forget different practices in their style: William BLAKE; MONSU DESIDERO; DÜRER with his "A Knight and Death"...

II-Many enigmatic and frankly dared paintings contain a tangle of different affects and a range of iconographic symbols: jealousy, aggressivity, despair...hypnotized states, turn of the tick or vivid creativity.

-All the dynamic psychic is often understood by depressive, melancholy feelings, may eliminate the time of the mental representation of the shape in favor of the direct projection of his emotions on the canvas in reason of an intimate spiritual life of the painter.

Nevertheless, as with the sick, perspective is often neglected.

About the Proximity of the Unconscious, notably of the Dreams's contents After a dream, sometimes after a nightmare: some works may be suggested or derived indirectly, which come out of it, is often of great or impressive strength. We cannot forget-It's also necessary to mention the two NEBUCHADNEZZAR's dreams about the composite statue and notably the fact that Giant appeared with clay's feet. From the impossible interpretation of margins, until DANIEL was able to precise the signification. the result was a proclamation throughout the whole empire of the right away sense of God. CALPUNIA's dream of the CESAR's marry the day before CESAR's assassination.

The Tales and the Myths are obvious fantasy condensed.

In other FIELDS

We cannot forget awesome creators discovering, for instance, the fact that solutions to equations could be found in this way:, Certainly from ARCHIMEDE; PYTHAGORE, THALES, Leonardo da VINCI and all those who find solutions to equations, as well as by H. POINCARÉ, K.F. GAUSS with regard to the law of induction and also DESCARTES in his philosophical conceptualization... the most famous astronomers, who may describe so much magnificent constellations in the sky A lot of gifted researchers would be long to cite as mathematics, digital license and high levels in sciences could represent/equal the beauty in the ARTS:

Among high conceptual WORKS in current sciences, many would deserve consideration here.

It will need an other study, because descriptions are so much various and related even more from more remote eras and civilizations.

-V-It's not to forget the AESTHETIC SHOCK arouse the discover of certain works:

It's diverse subjects between mediation and emotion: deep admiration and until pulsional destructive strength:

The Expression of EMOTIONS in the PAINTINGS of ARTISTIC MASTERS should be not Forget. But

all is not simple, clear, logical and the emotion, which overwhelms many writers and among them, some who even have been psychoanalysts. The theme of a work. They may also involve the pursuit of truth by thought and emotion.

That's the case also of STENDHAL contemplating the frescoes of FOSCOLO in the church of SANTA CROCE in FLORENCE-FIRENZE, with a great impressing feeling.

He said an other time: "if you never have seen this statue, you don't know the power of the sculpture."

A memory disorder marked by a disturbing strangeness by S. FREUD seized by the beauty of the site as he was looking on the Acropolis in ATHENS is famous [2] and he feels the need to describe the causality of his emotion, trying to give a faithful narration of his emotion, exclaiming.: "all of this exists really, as we learnt it at school..."

A character of PROUST: the critic BERGOTE finds a lively emotion at the contemplation of a work by VEERMER, a view of DELFT, which centers on small patch of yellow wall.

Even a psychoanalyst as LE GUEN before the "MOÏSE" of MICHEL-ANGE in Sankt Chapel of SANKT-Peter of the Links " in ROMA, who have published his real emotional impression in the frame of an article.

Artwork is not some enigma to be deciphered; its signification is due to the affective and emotional effort and in its organization in depends of a series of plans.

Other artists said later, for instance: "if you never have seen that masterpiece, you don't know the power of the sculpture."

-It's still some very important characteristics to evoke: the choice of the colors, the place on the sheet, the loss, sometimes on the center, the type of structuration of the drawn, which could be immediately symbolic. The painter of certain works can be recognized only seeing his work far away.

In musical work: their play and even the kind of sound, sad as grey mix or happy as different red.

The modeling of the clay can be also interesting.

-But the work of art can paradoxically arouse a negative active emotional and drive mobilization in a passage to the iconoclastic act. This was the case with the pounding of the *Pieta* by Leonard de VINCI in the Sankt Pier Cathedral in ROMA or by projection of bad substances or still recently, against the "Perl's Girl" of VERMEER.

Otherwise, many paintings may appear unexpected by their freedom inherent in the scenes presented, or even by the underlying eroticism, as well as enigmatic and frankly dared ones contain a tangle of different affects and a range of iconographic symbols: jealousy, aggressivity, despair....

We cannot forget the fact that other high conceptual WORKS in other fields. Morely in LITERATURE or in different shapes of arts after a dream or, eventually suggested or derived indirectly from the pregnancy of a nightmare. The dream involves the pursuit of truth by thought and emotion.

-It will need another study, because descriptions are so much various and related even more from more remote eras and civilizations. But all is not simple, clear, logical and the emotion, which overwhelms many writers and among them, some who even have been psychoanalysts.

VIII-The Strength of the Possession of an Artistic Masterpeace: Unconsciously reliving the creator's state of mind is the basis of aesthetic pleasure.

We have to take in consideration the pregnant power of Art, in its different expression, which sometimes borrow from memory of dreams, as well as from people, who have being painting without education in that field.

-It's even non utilitarian thefts for the purpose of appropriation, in particular of canvases. Even the famous psychoanalyst Jacques LACAN [4] kept behind one of their doors of his study "The creation of the world " of Gustav COURBET.

Unconsciously reliving the creator's state of mind is the basis of aesthetic pleasure

The fascination with the image or a sensation, such that the object is deprived of its representation is at work negatively in NARCISSE underlines P. AULAGNIER[1.]

For A.SEGAL, artistic creation can also be assimilated to a psychic equivalent of procreation.

CONCLUSION

This study try to approach of the different etiopathogeny's determinism of the creation of the artwork by mentally-ill subjects in the frame of hospitals or by yourself, often living alone.

and the positive reaction proposed by them in their writing or their picture or sculpture when the new quality of their works will be discovered. But, one of a deep reason, still no mention, of the creation is often is the search for the double, for the self, as did Camille CLAUDEL [14] in a paradigmatic way with her sculpture: "PERSEE and the GORGONE", while Paul CLAUDEL noted that the undeniable softening of the bill made it even more pathetic.

-The fascination with the image or the sensation, such that the object is deprived of its representations is at work negatively in NARCISSE underlines

P. AULAGNIER [1].

For A. SEGAL, artistic creation can also be assimilated to a psychic equivalent of procreation. Virtual lifetime and the game's world are contemporary pregnant and it seems that a new manner or obtain pleasure's level becomes quite addictive. It also by other means that some people denies the reality, more outside but bad, by the use of alcohol or drugs, as noramphetamine and even derealizing, searching new sensations and feelings by strange music or image and shows.

At contrary, some risk's taker keep a natural corporeality in acting, elsewhere are the limits in hard geographical or financial fields.

Care are now provide outside of specialized hospitals and the creativity time appears as a necessity to get a full life. A number of people without mental disorders research such places as well as wellness during their hard conditions of life.

The emergence of dared Contemporary Art owes a lot to the free organization of the pictures of Psychopathological Expression, relatives to the feelings of suffering people, incorporating different things/symptoms like fear, anxiety, depressive states, hallucinations, angry, various moods i.e. in their style as well as in the colors's choice to translate/represent the strength of emotion, affects and pulsions, I.e.

We think to works of the ART Cru=Raw ART; Abstract Expressionism Art, notably the One resulting of the Secession in 1897 by Gustav KLIMT in VIENNA, where was built the palace of Secession with this famous, prestigious and provocative Inscription/ "Der ZEIT ihre KUNST" "Der Kunst Ihre FREIHEIT"; as well as later the Modern Art, the Contemporary Art, including multiple sources of influences.

We could cite inventive/expressive free Art: Cubism by P. PICASSO, also Cubism linked/allied by Abstract and futurism by once again quoting master artists: S.DALI and, later....Time in which famous works are "turquoise marylin: Andy WHAROL; lock-myckey-roy: LICHTENSTEIN; Autum-Rythm: Jackson POLLOCK i.e.,, all that induced in notable part by the extremely fruitfull discovery of the hidden Production of mentally-ill, often due to acultural people, which was a long time underestimate.

But now, the art therapist should not seek to have masterful works of art copied, but rather provide some notions in technical production and, if necessary, reassure the novice creator surprised by his creation. The psychotherapist will be responsible for helping to articulate the emergence of emotion with the underlying unconscious conflict.

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Figure: Among the author's collections: shriek more as a Cry, interpretation en anglais of an very a anxious man, after an interpretation of a remembering in the frame of a psychotherapy

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